

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D 7.1: Data on type, quality, availability, and geographical distribution of agro-forest waste and by-products

REPORTING PERIOD	
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Deliverable D7.1 Responsible	Stefano Superchi (Unibas)
RM7 Responsible	Stefano Superchi

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Table 1 - List of Deliverables

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
D7.1	Data on type, quality, availability, and geographical distribution of agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report and a database on distribution and availability of biomass suitable for valorization	UNIBAS	PU	M12
D7.2	Delivery of validated extraction protocols according to the treated biomass type	R	Report on validated methodologies for value-added extracts depending on biomass type	UNIBAS	PU	M22
D7.3	Extracts and pure compounds suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.4	Extracts suitable as biopesticides	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.5	Report on bio-chemical characterization of biomass extracts and pure compounds	R		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.6	Biomaterials for bioactive extracts delivery	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.8	Formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.9	Formulates for agro-chemical applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report on validated methodologies suitable for scale-up and industrial production	UNIBAS	PU	M30

Table 2 - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M7.1	Survey on regional scale of the type, quality, availability, distribution of biomass from agro-forest waste	7	8	Report
M7.2	Selection of biomass materials suitable for valorization (at least three)	7	10	Report
M7.3	Validation of extraction protocols for selected matrices and materials	7	12	Report
M7.4	Availability of biomass extracts (at least five) suitable for bio-activity tests	7	16	Material
M7.5	Production of a report on bioactivity of different materials and compounds	7	20	Report
M7.6	Availability of biomaterials for bioactive material delivery	7	26	Material
M7.8	Availability of formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	7	28	Material
M7.9	Availability of formulates for agro-chemical applications	7	28	Material
M7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	7	30	Report

A) INTRODUCTION

Aim of the activity of the Research Module 7 is the valorization of waste and by-products from the agro-forest industry for the production of valuable chemicals and intermediates to be employed in the pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic industry, as well as bio-pesticides for sustainable agriculture. This activity will focus on the agro-forest production of the Basilicata region, taken as a model of the typical agricultural production of the regions of southern Italy. In fact, despite Basilicata has a smaller total cultivated area in respect to the largest neighboring regions, i.e. Campania, Calabria, and Puglia, it presents in a relatively restricted area all the typical orographic, climate, and environmental features of the southern regions. This reflects in the diversity of the agricultural productions which spans from the forestall activity, to cereals, to olive oil and wine production, to vegetables and fruits (orange, lemon, tangerine, peaches, apricots, strawberries, etc...).

The climate of the region is influenced by three factors that determine as many climatic differences, which can be framed in the geographical layout of the region, influenced by the three Ionian, Adriatic and Tyrrhenian seas. In the first case, which includes the coastal strip of the Metapontino up to the first hill close to it, there are mild winters, dry summers and little rainfall during the year (less than 500 mm); in the second case, which includes the eastern part of the region, a semi-continental climate is observed with notable diurnal and seasonal temperature variations, with more accentuated rainfall (around 600–700 mm) and a colder winter while the summer is dry and very hot with peaks of up to 45°. The Tyrrhenian influence is part of the third climatic factor, including the western part of Basilicata up to the Val d'Agri, with mild winters on the coasts, while in the mountains there are very cold temperatures and windy summers, rainfall is abundant and equally divided during all year round (1500 mm with peaks of 2000 mm). Finally, the last factor is that of altitude, in fact from 600 meters above sea level onwards there is a continental climate with very harsh winters and cool and often rainy summers (800-1000 mm per year). Frequent winter snowfalls are present both in the mountains part of the region and in the high hills.

Based on the habitats Basilicata can be divided into 5 sub-areas:

Vulture-Melfese to the north-east, with plateaus mostly sown with wheat, while, in the Vulture area, it highlights alternating woods and hills that are well suited to viticulture;

Potentino/Lucane Dolomites/Val d'Agri, to the north-north-west, with a prevalence of woods and mountains with an average height of 1200-1500 metres;

Pollino Massif/Monte Sirino to the south-west, which represent the true Lucanian mountains, with altitudes even higher than 2000 meters and a notable presence of forests and woods;

Matera hill, in the centre-east, which has hills and high hills, with a large presence of barren clay and gullies;

Metapontino, to the south-south-east, a vast alluvial plain characterized by intensive industrial agriculture and a type of low and sandy coast.

These geographical diversifications are also expressed in a peculiar biodiversity.

Figure 1. Physical map of Basilicata

The main farming activities in Basilicata region deal with the production of wine, olive oil, and fruits (citrus, peaches, apricots, strawberries) as well as cereals. These agro-industries, together with the well-developed forest-industry annually produces large amount of vegetable waste and by-products which constitute a relevant economic and environmental problem for their disposal. Aim of the RM 7 is the recovery of valuable chemical compounds from these agro-forest wastes. Basilicata region has a geographic surface of 999224 ha with a mostly rural territory, a population of about 580000 inhabitants and one of the lowest regional population densities in Italy (57.8 inhabitants per km²). The total agricultural area is 489229 ha (accounting for 48.96% of the regional surface area); 368726 ha are used for agriculture, of which 57.72% is used for arable crops and 10.77% for orchards, mainly in hilly areas. The 31.28% remaining surface area is characterized by permanent grassland, especially in mountain areas. Therefore, Basilicata region display a high potential for the recovery and valorization of agro-forest waste. However, at present, the only investigations on amount and type of agro-forest waste available carried out focused on the potential of biomasses for energy production, while studies on the potentiality of agro-forest waste recovery and valorization were completely lacking. Moreover, no regional databases reporting type, amount, availability, and valorization potential of such waste were available.

For this reason, the activity of RM 7 started with the data collection on agro-forest waste and by-products production on regional scale of Basilicata, the region where the Task leader Unibas is located. The aim was to set up a regional database on agro-forest waste which could help to select the most promising waste type to study for valorization. The parameters taken into account were i) the available amount on regional basis, ii) the potentiality for valuable products recovery, iii) the environmental impact of waste disposal. Data on type, surface, quantity, and geographical distribution of agricultural crops of the region were collected together with data on the corresponding quantity, availability, current method of disposal, and environmental impact of waste and by-products derived. Particular attention was focused on waste and by-products coming from wine, olive oil, vegetable, and fruit production, while cereal production was not considered. This because waste from wine, olive oil, vegetables and fruits production appeared most promising for the recovery of bioactive valuable products. Waste and by-products suitable for treatment and recovery, should also be selected taking into account also the producers demand in terms of economic and environmental cost of disposal.

B) SURVEY METHODOLOGY

Data on agricultural production were collected taking into account available databases on national and regional scale such as those of SIAN¹ (National Agricultural Information System), ISTAT² (National Institute of Statistics), and the annual report of CREA³ (Council for agricultural research and analysis of agricultural economics) (see, for example, Charts A1.1-A1.14 in the ANNEX 1). Moreover, those data were integrated with information from “Assessorato per le politiche agricole, alimentari e forestali” of Regione Basilicata.⁴

Data on agriculture crops waste production were not already available. Therefore, a statistical survey obtained directly contacting farmers and transformers of agriculture products was carried out (see ANNEX 2). The addresses were obtained from the regional Camera di Commercio, which provided us a list of nearly 3000 companies with addresses, type of crop production, telephone and emails contacts.

The agricultural companies to be contacted were selected from the whole list on the basis of their activities and production type, as stated by the corresponding ATECO code (see Table 1).

Table 1. ATECO Code of agricultural companies selected to administer the survey.

ATECO Code	Descrizione
01.11.2	Coltivazione di semi oleosi
01.11.20	Coltivazione di semi oleosi
01.13.1	Coltivazione di ortaggi in foglia, a fusto, a frutto, in radici, bulbi e tuberi in piena aria
01.13.10	
01.13.2	
01.13.20	
1.21	Coltivazione di uva
1.23	Coltivazione di agrumi
1.24	Coltivazione di pomacee e frutta a nocciolo
1.25	Coltivazione di altri alberi da frutta, frutti di bosco e in guscio
1.26	Coltivazione di frutti oleosi
10.32	Produzione di succhi di frutta e di ortaggi
10.39	Altra Lavorazione e conservazione di frutta e di ortaggi
10.41.1	Produzione di olio di oliva da olive prevalentemente non di produzione propria
10.41.10	Produzione di olio di oliva da olive prevalentemente non di produzione propria
10.41.2	Produzione di olio raffinato o grezzo da semi oleosi o frutti oleosi prevalentemente non di produzione propria
11.01	Distillazione, rettifica e miscelatura degli alcolici
11.02	Produzione di vini da uve

Collaboration with farms consortia and associations was also established, to get their help to administer the survey to the associates.

Some of the consortia contacted are the following:

- Consorzio di tutela Aglianico del Vulture;
- Consorzio di tutela Terre d'Alta Val d'Agri;
- Enoteca Regionale Lucana;
- Consorzio di tutela Grottino di Roccanova;
- Repertorio oli extravergini della Basilicata;

The survey administered to the agricultural companies involved in the selected crop production required answers to the following questions:

1. Name of the company, legal status, address of the registered office;
2. Type of crop produced;
3. Production period;
4. Cultivated area in the region (ha);
5. Location of the culture within the region;
6. Overall crops production (q/tons/ha);
7. Main use (direct use/transformation);
8. Main waste type;
9. Amount of waste produced (q/tons/ha);
10. Current methodology for disposal and/or reuse of waste produced;

Two more different version of the survey with specific focus on wine and oil production were prepared, to better target these important agricultural productions for Basilicata region. These specific surveys were administered to the companies by means of the Consortia and Associations of wine and oil producers.

The survey was administered by resorting to the Google Form tool. This allowed to obtain a single database with all the answers and a useful tool for processing the data. In fact, Google Form tool can automatically generate an Excel sheet with all the data sorted and ready to be analyzed. Additionally, in this way the survey is administered simply emailing the survey link instead of sending a document to be filled. This makes the survey easier and quicker to be filled by the administrative offices of the companies involved, which are quite often very small.

The administration of the survey allowed to gather data on amount and type of waste produced for the different crops as well as to get information on the current methodology of waste disposal and/or reuse. When data from the survey were not complete or not statistical reliable, we estimated the waste production by resorting to literature data or literature models of estimation methodologies⁵ where the authors developed a model to estimate waste production for specific crops.

Such data has been then collected in the following Report (Deliverable 7.1) providing a valuable tool to select the most suitable waste biomass to be investigated for recovery and valorization in the following Research Module Tasks.

C) ANALYSIS OF WASTE PRODUCTION OF MAIN REGIONAL CROPS

As inferred from Table 2 and Figure 2 about half of the cultivated area of Basilicata is dedicated to cereals cultivation, while the remaining part is dedicated to grape, olives, fruits and vegetables. However, the cereals waste is mainly composed of lignocellulosic materials, which

are not suitable for the recovery of valuable bioactive by-products, which is the main goal of RM7 research activity. Moreover, The highest waste production is obtained from agricultural productions which require crop transformations for the preparation of derivatives, like wine, oil, juices, etc. Therefore, we concentrated our investigation to the most promising agriculture productions from the point of view of the waste recovery and valorization, discarding the production of cereals and vegetables which are directly delivered to the market without transformation processes.

This restricted our investigation to the production of wine, olive oil and transformed fruits like pomegranate, strawberry, hazelnut, and pistachio.

Table 2. Overall Agricultural productions of Basilicata

Crop	cultivated area (ha)	production (tons)
cereals	123523	350195
olives	26086	30736
grapes	2516	30651
fruit	8083	126170
vegetables	5726	205422
vegetables in greenhouse	30982	8410
strawberries	38589	12105
citrus fruits	5814	100534

Figure 2. Overall Agricultural productions of Basilicata: (left) cultivated area (ha); (right) produced quantity (tons).

CI. WINE PRODUCTION

CI.1 Introduction

Basilicata is a region mostly made of mountain and hills, with only 8% of plains, with a lot of territory that well suited the production of wine. In the south area of Vulture, a dormant volcano, is located the origin of Apennines rocks chain, to west is located the Maddalena, in the east the landscape is formed by hills subjected to continuous erosions phenomena. The plains are located mostly on Jonic sea side, in a territory called Metapontino, originated from erosion material of the many rivers of Basilicata. The mild winter climate in the metapontino is ideal for the cultivation of white grapes, like Greco and Malvasia. On the hills side starts the production of more structured wines, like Primitivo, whereas in the river vales we found Merlot, Cabernet sauvignon and Sangiovese. On the mountain side, especially in the volcanic area of Vulture, we finally found the production of Aglianico, the most famous DOCG wine of Basilicata.

Table 3. The total grape and wine production of Basilicata in 2020 (Data from Annuario ISTAT, Chart A1.4 in ANNEX 1):

Wine grape Total cultivated area (ha)	Total wine grape production (q.)	Total wine production (hl.) ^{a,b}
2000	182280	85000
		46,6%

^a31 % DOP, 31% IGP, 82% red wine and 18% white wines;

^bAwarded wines: 1 DOCG, 4 DOC, 1 IGT.

While the geographical distribution of grape production is reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Grape Cultivation Distribution in Basilicata

Figure 4. Areas of DOC wines of Basilicata: (1) Aglianico del Vulture Superiore, (2) Aglianico del Vulture, (3) Grotтино di Roccanova, (4) Matera, (5) Terre dell'Alta Val d'Agri.

C1.2 Potential for wine production waste recovery and valorization

From these production data an estimated wine production yield of approximately 67% (121,000 hl of wine from 182,280 tons of wine grapes). However, data regarding the production of grape pomace, cream of tartar (potassium bitartrate, particularly present in wine dregs and sediment), and other residues were not available.

For this reason, data on wine waste were obtained submitting a statistical survey directly to the local wine producers, with the aim to estimate and extrapolate the data.

Therefore, a Google Forms survey (see Methodology) was sent to 500 companies, 260 of which were further contacted by phone due to the initial low response rate to the survey.

The collected data from the survey are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Data on wine production from survey responses.

	Area coltivata (ha)	Comune di produzione	Produzione complessiva (q)	Scarto di Raspi (q)	Scarto di Vinacce (q)	Scarto di Fecce (q)	Attuale Metodologia di Smaltimento e/o Riutilizzo dello Scarto Prodotto
1	800	Venosa	40000	1350	5850	2250	Raspi come Concime, Vinacce Distilleria, Fecce Distilleria
2	7	Ginestra	100	0	62,5	7,5	spandimento in vigna
3	5	Rionero in V., Ripacandida	200	20	140	25	legna da ardere
4	13	Barile, Ripacandida	800	80	80	80	Conferimento in distilleria
5	15	Barile, Ripacandida, Maschito	900	27	45	135	interramento in campo
6	25	Barile, Maschito	2000	60	300	40	spandimento in vigna
7	6	Roccanova	250	18	73	15,4	spandimento in vigna
8	50	Maschito, Ginestra, Barile, Ripacandida, Rionero	3500	175	525	350	distillazione
9	10	Melfi, Rionero in Vulture	800	24	96	40	Conferimento in distilleria
10	4	Rapolla	100	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	spandimento in vigna
11	3,2	Scanzano Jonico	300	15	30	18	Conferimento in distilleria
12	20	Barile	600	18	120	30	n.d.
13	28	Montalbano Jonico	1400	28	252	72	spandimento in vigna
14	14	Viggiano	660	33	86	50	spandimento in vigna
15	4	Senise	200	30	8	12	n.d.
16	31,2	Montescaglioso	1770	12	36	11	spandimento in vigna
17	7,5	Barile	400	20	50	20	Raspi per compostaggio, Vinacce spandimento in vigna, Fecce Conferimento in distilleria
	1042,9		53980	1910	7753,5	3155,9	
				3,54	14,36	5,85	% rispetto a produzione

The total grape production recorded (53980 q) accounts for 29.6% of the total for wine grapes in the Basilicata region (182280 q), while the total cultivated area recorded accounts for 52% of the total for wine grapes in the Basilicata region (1043 hectares recorded out of 2027 hectares total). Therefore, even if the full wine regional production was not covered by the survey the collected data were statistical solid enough to obtain an accurate estimation of the regional availability of waste coming from wine production.

Table 5. Data from the survey responses from Basilicata wine producers.

Total cultivated area (hectares)	Total grape production (q.)	Total grape stalks (q.)	Total wine pomace (q.)	Totale wine lees (q.)
1043	53980	1910	7753	3156
		3,54%	14,36%	5,85%

From the collected data in Table 5, it derives that grape stalks, grape pomace, and grape lees represent 3.54%, 14.36%, and 5.85% of the total grape production, respectively. According to the recorded data, the quantity of wine produced represents 63% of the wine grape production, in agreement with the total data in Table 2. Based on the percentages obtained from the collected data and the regional total amounts in Table 3, it is possible to estimate the total production of waste from the wine production reported in Table 6.

Table 6. Estimated data for waste wine production in Basilicata.

Total cultivated area (h)	Total grape production (q.)	Total grape stalks (q.)	Total wine pomace (q.)	Totale wine lees (q.)
2000	182280	6452	26175	10663

In the last 20 years, several grape pomace exploitation alternatives were studied, mainly focusing on the extraction and further valorization of high-value compounds present in this by-product. In fact, during winemaking only a minor part of grape phytochemicals is extracted into the wine, leaving the pomace still rich in phenolic compounds (mainly flavonoids, phenolic acids, stilbenes and anthocyanins), dietary fibers, proteins, lipids and minerals.¹⁻⁴ Many of these compounds exert ascertained positive effects on human health⁴ and show a great potential of being applied as ingredients in the food, nutraceutical, pharmaceutical and cosmetic fields. Other components can be exploited as colorants, antioxidant or antimicrobial agents, or in packaging formulations.^{1,2,4,5,6}

As inferred from Table 3 the current method of disposing of wine waste, as observed in surveys, involves composting for grape stalks, agronomic spreading for grape pomace, and sending the grape lees to the distillery. However, all the types of waste obtained during wine production deserve an extremely high potential for valorization being very rich of valuable bioactive metabolites. Below is reported a short survey on the bioactive compounds content and properties of wine making waste.

Grape Pomace

Taking into account their high content of phenolic compounds, which are known for their antioxidant and antimicrobial potential, grape pomace by-products such as skin and seeds can

be used as sources of natural additives, which can be employed in the development of many products ranging from medical to food applications (Table 7).⁷⁻¹⁰

The high concentration of phenolic compounds in grape by-products occurs as a result of insufficient extraction in winemaking.¹¹ Phenolic compounds are divided in two main classes: flavonoids, presenting as subclasses anthocyanins, flavanols, flavan-3-ols, flavones and chalcones; and non-flavonoids, which are split into phenolic acids, stilbenes, tannins, coumarins and neolignanes.

Table 7 Main compounds found in grape waste.

Compound	Material	Value	Reference
(+)-Catechin	Pomace (skin and seed)	5083 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	12
(-)-Epicatechin	Pomace (skin and seed)	192.8 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	12
Quercetin	Pomace (skin and seed)	650.2 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	12
Myricetin	Pomace (skin and seed)	452 ppm dry extract	13
Rutin	Pomace (skin and seed)	998.5 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	12
Kaempferol	Pomace (skin and seed)	346.8 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	12
Gallic acid	Pomace (skin and seed)	1090.1 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	12
Ellagic acid	Grape skin	0.73 mg kg^{-1} dry weight	14
	Grape seed	10.74 mg kg^{-1} dry weight	14
Syringic acid	Pomace (skin and seed)	1731.7 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15
Caffeic acid	Pomace (skin and seed)	16.0 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15
p-Coumaric acid	Pomace (skin and seed)	64.6 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15
Ferulic acid	Pomace (skin and seed)	24.1 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15
Caftaric acid	Pomace (skin and seed)	1.80 mg kg^{-1} dry weight	16
Quercetin 3-glucuronide	Pomace (skin and seed)	81.42 mg kg^{-1} dry weight	16
trans-Resveratrol	Pomace (skin and seed)	36.0 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15
Delphinidin 3-O-glucoside	Pomace (skin and seed)	4581 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15
Cyanidin 3-O-glucoside	Pomace (skin and seed)	870 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15
Malvidin 3-O-glucoside	Pomace (skin and seed)	26,658 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15
Cyanidin 3-O-p-coumaroylglucoside	Pomace (skin and seed)	1886 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ extract	15

The antimicrobial activity associated with grapes and wines is well established and their action is related to the presence of phenolic compounds, which are mainly composed of hydroxycinnamic acids, gallic acid, flavonols, flavan-3-ols and trans-resveratrol.¹⁷ Flavonols are considered the main phenolic compounds in grapes, with high antimicrobial potential. Besides being able to inhibit virulence factors, they also have a synergistic effect with antibiotics.¹⁸ They are mainly present in grape seeds, in which the most abundant ones are kaempferol 3-O-glucoside, quercetin 3-O-glucoside, quercetin and myricetin.¹⁹

Regarding the antioxidant potential attributed to phenolic compounds, this can be related to the inactivation of free radicals by hydrogen and individual electron-transferring reactions. The use of extracts in foods may decrease microbial proliferation and, due to antioxidant and antimicrobial potential, can increase product safety and shelf life, grape pomace extracts significantly decreased *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Micrococcaceae* counts, besides yeasts and molds, which was attributed to the antimicrobial potential related to the presence of phenolic compounds.²⁰

Grape Lees

According to literature and EEC regulation No. 337/79, wine lees can be defined as “a residue that is formed at the bottom of wine containers, after fermentation, during storage or after treatments, as well as the residue obtained after the filtration or centrifugation of this product”.²¹ The main characteristics of wine lees are acidic pH (between 3 and 6), a chemical oxygen demand above 30,000 mg/L, potassium levels around 2500 mg/L, and phenolic compounds in amounts up to 1000 mg/L.²²

Individual phenolic compounds belonging to flavonoids (flavanols, flavonols, and anthocyanins), phenolic acids, and stilbenes have been identified and quantified in wine lees. Wine lees are a reliable source of flavonols such as quercetin, quercitrin, kaempferol, and myricetin. According to literature,²³ the major flavonol is quercetin with an amount of 42 µg/g DM, while kaempferol and myricetin show lower values (10 and 8 µg/g DM, respectively). Other flavonols detected in wine lees include kaempferol 3-(2',3'-diacetylramnoside)-7"-rhamnoside, quercetin 3-O-glucoside, quercetin 3-O-glucuronide, quercetin 3-O-galactoside and quercetin 3-O-rutinoside.²⁴⁻²⁶ In wine lees from *Vitis labrusca* varieties, laricitrin, isorhamnetin, and syringetin, and their glucosides, as well as myricetin derivatives (myricetin 3-O-glucuronide and myricetin 3-O-glucoside) were found.²⁴ In a paper on characterization of wine lees by liquid chromatography and mass spectrometry, flavanols, namely catechin, epicatechin, and procyanidin B2, were tentatively identified, but these compounds were not quantified.²⁵ In other studies, the content of catechin was 4 µg/g DM²⁷ and 121 µg/mL wine lees extract.²⁶ These concentrations were low in comparison with other compounds present in the samples, such as quercetin (42 µg/g DM and 1216 µg/mL wine lees extract, respectively). Anthocyanins have been identified in wine lees. Up to total of 26 anthocyanins were determined in samples of wine lees: derivatives of the anthocyanidins delphinidin, cyanidin, petunidin, peonidin and malvidin. In *Vitis vinifera* varieties, delphinidin-3-O-glucoside, petunidin-3-O-glucoside, peonidin-3-O-glucoside, malvidin-3-O-glucoside, malvidin-3-O-galactoside, delphinidin-3-O-(6"-p-acetylglucoside), cyanidin-3-O-(6"-p-acetylglucoside), malvidin-3-O-(6"-p-acetylglucoside), delphinidin-3-O-(6"-p-coumaroyl-glucoside), petunidin-3-O-(6"-p-coumaroyl-glucoside), malvidin-3-O-(6"-p-coumaroyl-glucoside) and pelargonidin-3-(6"-p-coumaroyl-glucoside) were found.^{25,28,29} Among these compounds, malvidin-3-O-glucoside and malvidin-3-(6"-p-coumaroylglucoside) were in higher concentrations in wine lees.²⁸ Regarding phenolic acids, caffeic acid and *p*-coumaric acid and their derivatives such as *trans*-caftaric acid and *trans*-coutaric acid, respectively, have been found in wine lees samples, being caffeic acid and *trans*-caftaric acid the predominant compounds in both *Vitis vinifera* and non-vinifera varieties.^{24,27} Moreover, hydroxybenzoic acids have been reported: gallic and vanillic acids.^{25,27} All acids were found in concentrations ranging between 1 and 6 µg/g DM, for gallic acid and caffeic acid, respectively. Resveratrol, *cis*- and *trans*-resveratrol, is a stilbene that has been extensively identified in skin of grapes, however its identification in wine lees is less common. This compound has been reported by some authors

but at lower concentrations than other phenolics.^{24,26} Phenolic compounds in wine lees show different antioxidant activities for different assays and therefore lees are a good source of antioxidant compounds that can delay the oxidation of macromolecules.²⁸

Grape Stalks

Grape stalks are the grape lignocellulosic skeleton of grapes that are obtained from stripping operations during processing. Stalks are the main by-products of vineyards and represent between 2.5% and 7.5% of weight of grapes.^{30,31} Grape stalks contain higher polyphenolics content than other vegetable by-products such as wheat straw but similar to that reported for green tea³² grape stalks non-polar extractives are mainly composed by saturated fatty acids, with the most abundant being palmitic acid (hexadecanoic acid, 23-30%), followed by stearic (octadecanoic, 6-7%) and eicosanoic (2-3%) acids. Glycerol and long chain alcohols were also found in considerable proportion (11-29%). Some unsaturated acids, diacids, sterols and terpenes were also identified but in lower percentage.³² In a preliminary study, Spigno et al.³³ concluded that grape stalks were a promising cellulose source even though additional research is needed to optimize extraction procedure. Grape stalks wastes could also be a good source of natural polyphenolic compounds.³²

C2. OLIVE OIL PRODUCTION

C2.1 Introduction

Basilicata represents one of the Italian regions with the greatest vocation in the cultivation of olive trees and in the production of olive oil, contributing significantly to national and particularly southern production. The areas of Basilicata where the production of olives and oil is most concentrated are the Vulture-Melfese, the lower Collina Materana and the lower Val d'Agri. Consequently, oil mills are very widespread (more than 150) throughout the entire regional territory. For these oil production plants the problem of waste treatment and disposal, as well as that connected to their possible valorization, is extremely important.

Figure 5. Distribution of Olive Mills in Basilicata

The main by-products of olive processing are pomace and vegetation water. Virgin pomace is the solid by-product of the mechanical processing of olives. Generally, through an extraction process with solvents followed by distillation and rectification, oil and spent pomace are obtained from it. Pomace oil, although used for food purposes, is obviously much less valuable and profitable than extra virgin oil, also requiring an energy expenditure ten times higher than that necessary to obtain extra virgin oil through mechanical extraction from olives. The exhausted pomace is a product that can be used as a source of thermal energy or find a useful use in the feed sector. Currently, the exhausted pomace is also used for the manufacture of bricks and for the production of furfural used as a solvent for the paint industry.

Vegetation water represents the liquid by-product of olive processing, the quantity of which, in relation to the extraction cycle used, varies from 40-55 liters per 100 kg of olives processed with the pressure extraction system, to 80-120 liters per 100 kg of olives processed with the centrifugation system. Vegetation water is composed of the water contained in the fruit and the water used for washing the olives and for the extraction process, as well as pulp and oil residues. The polluting load of this wastewater is attributable to its high value of COD (between 45 and 220 g l⁻¹) and BOD₅ (between 35 and 100 g l⁻¹), its low pH (4-5) and its high concentration of compounds recalcitrant to biological degradation, such as lignin, tannins, long-chain fatty acids and phenolic compounds. The latter, of which the vegetation water is very rich (3-10 g l⁻¹), are mainly responsible for its phytotoxicity and difficult biological degradation. The disposal of this waste represents a considerable burden for oil mills, given the strict laws (Law 574/96) for the protection of the environment which prevent the discharge of waste from agro-industrial processing processes into waterways or the urban sewer system. One of the methods of reusing

vegetation water consists in the controlled and limited spreading of the wastewater on agricultural land. In fact, these waters contain natural biodegradable plant substances which bring organic matter and fertilizing mineral elements to the soil. However, to avoid negative effects, spreading on land requires very stringent conditions of use regarding the type of crops, the spreading period, the concentrations used and the nature of the soil as well as specific authorization procedures. Among the clean techniques for treating vegetation water, the evaporation-condensation technique is also considered. This technique is based on the evaporation by heating the vegetation water, thus allowing the organic substances to be concentrated and products for the food, pharmaceutical and cosmetics industries to be obtained. Plants based on concentration by evaporation technically allow compliance with current legislation, but at very high costs.

The extraction technologies used influence all the products of the olive industry. Oil extraction is achieved through the crushing of the drupes until they are reduced to paste, from which, through the adoption of appropriate separation technologies, the oil is isolated from its by-products. Analyzing the process just described in more detail, we can distinguish the phases of storage, defoliation and washing, crushing, extraction of the oil must, and separation of the oil.

(a) Storage. The olives are stored in a cool, well-aerated environment, preferably protected from light and heat sources to prevent problems with the deterioration of the drupes (overheating, bruising, mold or fermentation, etc.). (b) Defoliation and washing. This operation, carried out using vibrating screens often coupled with aspirators, is necessary to avoid the accumulation of leaves or other plant debris, but also to remove any foreign bodies (soil, stones, woody residues, etc.) present in the mass to be processed. The washing operation, recommended to improve the appearance and healthiness of the fruits collected from the ground, can be detrimental if carried out on olives in an advanced state of ripeness due to the easier disintegration of the fruit cuticle in contact with water. These two steps essentially produces a waste composed by leaves and small wood residues. (c) Crushing or milling. The purpose of olive milling is to obtain a homogeneous paste whose consistency depends essentially on the degree of moisture it possesses. This is done using traditional stone mills or crushers. The former, by crushing the mass through the rotational movement of a grinder, also facilitate its mixing. With crushing, on the other hand, there is an instantaneous breaking of the pulp and the pit through a perforated ring where the olive is forcefully pushed. (d) Kneading. With kneading, the olive paste is continuously stirred to facilitate the oil's extraction. The required time is approximately 30 minutes if associated with milling, but it can extend to over 60 minutes if it follows crushing. The longer stirring time and the consequent increase in operating temperature, on one hand, lead to an increase in oil yield, but on the other hand, can result in a qualitative deterioration of the product due to the enhancement of thermo-oxidative processes responsible for the decrease in polyphenols and vitamin E and the increase in peroxides. (e) Extraction of the oil

must and oil separation. The solid-liquid separation can be achieved through two main extraction systems.

- Batch system or pressing: This is the most traditional method, in which the separation of the two phases, solid and liquid, occurs through vertical presses that, thanks to the significant applied pressure and the use of special discs (*fiscoli*), facilitate the extraction of the oily must.
- Continuous system or centrifugal: This involves the use of a horizontal centrifuge, the decanter, which allows the separation of the oily must from the olive pomace based on the different density of the two materials. The further processing of the oily must aims to separate the vegetation waters from the oil, but also to remove any coarse materials (residues of paste or mucilage) still present.

In the traditional system, extraction can occur by settling in specific tanks or, more commonly, by centrifugal separation. Traditional milling processes require water quantities ranging from 40 to 120 liters per quintal of crushed olives, to be added during stirring, generating a significant amount of wastewater. In the case of continuous plants, however, the oil must exiting the decanter is automatically fed to a centrifugal separator. This extraction system, now also known as the "three-phase system," provides for the initial separation of the olive pomace from the olive paste and, subsequently, for the removal of the vegetation waters from the oil. "Two-phase" separation systems have had limited success, at least in our country, where, already at the decanter level, the paste is split into oil and wet pomace (a mixture of pomace and vegetation waters). The higher oil content remaining in the wastewater and the high moisture content characterizing the olive pomace (55-65%) make this material unattractive to pomace processing plants and, at the same time, unsuitable for disposal on agricultural land due to its excessive fat content. Working instead with three phases, pomace with acceptable moisture levels (48-54%) and high quantities of vegetation waters can be obtained, which with the latest generation decanters (water-saving and short-cone) can be significantly reduced.

Table 8. Mill waste water production with different extraction technology.

Extraction Technology	Olives (kg)	Added Water (lt)	Pomace (kg)	Mill waste water (lt)
Traditional two phases	100	0-10	75-80	-
Traditional three phases	100	50	55-57	80-110
Water saving three phases	100	10-20	50-60	33-35

C2.2 Potential for olive oil production waste recovery and valorization

Analysis of the ISTAT national database reveals that about 57500 q of oil are produced, valued at 13.3 million euros. However, data regarding the production of olive pomace and other residues are not available.

In Table 9 the total productions of olives and olive oil for the Basilicata region and their respective production areas are reported:

Table 9. The total olive and olive oil production of Basilicata (Data from Annuario ISTAT 2023, see Figure A1.3 in ANNEX 1):

Olives Total cultivated area (ha)	Total olive production (q.)	Total olive oil production (q.)
27300	322444	57549

On national scale, the produced olive oil represents 18% w/w of the olives and produced pomace is about 1.54 times the oil production. This allow to estimate the production of pomace from the total olive production in the Basilicata region to be yearly around 88600 q (Table 11).

National data regarding the production of olive stones and mill waste water are not available. Therefore, we extrapolated these data from the delivered survey (Table 10).

The collected data (Table 10) represent approximately 12% of the total olive production in the Basilicata region (38,528 q recorded out of a total of 322444 q). Based on the collected data, over 80% is represented by pomace oil (31,605 q), the olive stones represents 27% (10,270 q), and the waste waters is 50% compared to the olives produced (19,023 q).

Based on this data, it can be estimated that the total olive pomace produced in the Basilicata region amounts to approximately 88600 q, olive stones would represent 33800 q, and the mill waste water produced should reach approximately 29000 q.

Table 10. Data on olive oil production from survey responses.

	Total oil production	Pomace	olive stones	mill waste water
1	10678	15755	9000	395
2	5000	5000	500	0
3	7000	3500	0	5600
4	400	0	0	0
5	7500	3500	0	3500
6	7800	2600	770	8000
7	150	1250	0	1528
Total	38528	31605	10270	19023

Table 11. Estimation of waste of olive oil production in Basilicata.

Total olive oil production (q)	pomace (q)	Olive stones (q)	Mill waste water
57549	88600	33800	29.000

Currently, based on the survey responses, the olive nuts are sold as fuel for biomass boilers. The water and wet destoned pomace are delivered to companies that employ them for biogas energy production. The waste leaves are sent for recovery with the CER code 020304, unusable waste for consumption and processing.

Regardless of its negative environmental impacts, the potential added value of olive oil waste for numerous sectors is well known, even if there are a few reviews reporting the different applications for olive wastes in the literature.^{1,2}

Olive byproducts are abundant sources of bioactive phenolic compounds³⁻⁶ that have promising potential as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial agents.⁷⁻⁹ Hence, the recovery of phenolic compounds from these wastes, after suitable purification, presents considerable interest for food and beverage,¹⁰⁻¹² cosmetic,¹³⁻¹⁵ and nutraceutical¹⁶ industries, due to their interesting pharmaceutical properties.

Other way to valorize olive wastes is to convert them into inexpensive adsorbents for water pollution control,¹⁷ in particular, heavy metals;¹⁸ moreover, the ability of these biosorbents to adsorb several metal ions may increase their potential application on industrial waste water treatment.¹⁹

Olive Pomace

Cioffi et al.²⁰ reported oleuropein (81.7–83.9 mg/kg of dry weight) and ligstroside aglycone (27.1–31.1 mg/kg of dry weight) as the most abundant compounds of olive pomace from Cilento National Park (Italy). In olive pomace from Algeria, oleuropein (144 mg/g of dry weight) was also detected as the major compound, and secoxyloganin (55 mg/g of dry weight), loganin (47 mg/g of dry weight), and cyanidin-3-glucoside (39 mg/g of dry weight) were observed for the first time in olive wastes.²¹ On the other hand, Madureira et al.²² described hydroxytyrosol (25 mg/g of extract) as the main phenolic compound present in olive pomace from the region of Alentejo (Portugal), followed by hydroxytyrosol. 1- β -glucoside (9.8 mg/g of extract) and tyrosol (5.9 mg/g of extract), which is consistent with the observations made by Malapert et al.²³ These authors also described hydroxytyrosol (370.7 mg/L), hydroxytyrosol glucoside (165.2 mg/L), and tyrosol (148.4 mg/L) as the major compounds present in olive pomace from Baux-de-Provence (France). Additionally, Nunes et al.⁵ observed that hydroxytyrosol and comsegolosite represented about 79% of the total phenolics present in olive pomace from the region of Trás-Os-Montes (Portugal). On the other hand, Rubio-Senent et al.²⁴ observed high quantities of 3,4 dihydroxyphenylglycol, elenolic acid derivatives, and comsegolosite besides hydroxytyrosol and

tyrosol. Furthermore, verbascoside, gallic acid, caffeic acid, vanillic acid, oleuropein aglycone, p-coumaric acid, rutin, luteolin-7-O-rutinoside, and luteolin-7-O-glucoside were reported in lower amounts.^{20,22,23,24}

Table 10 describes the main phenolic compounds found in olive pomace and their relative health effects.²⁵

Table 12. Health effect of some phenolic compound in olive pomace.²⁵

Phenolic group	compound	Health effects
Phenylalcohols	Hydroxytyrosol	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-aging agent; Anticancer properties; Antimicrobial properties; Protector against cardiovascular diseases; Protector against high cholesterol; Protector against digestive disorders; Skin protector; Prevention and treatment of osteoporosis; Prevention of HIV infection and/or HIV-derived diseases
	Tyrosol	Muscle damage inhibitor Cholesterol efflux promotor Intestine mucosa protector Anti-diabetic properties Prevention of hypertension Protector against cardiovascular diseases Prevention of osteopenia
Secoiridoids	Oleuropein	Anti-oxidant properties Blood pressure lowering Protector against cardiovascular diseases Neuroprotective properties Anticancer properties Antimicrobial properties Skin protector; Hepato protective properties Gastroprotective properties Anti-diabetic properties Anti-obesity properties Prevention of osteoporosis
Phenylethanoid	Verbascoside	Anti oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties Anticancer properties Hepato protective properties Wound healing properties Anti-hypertensive activity Anti-diabetic properties Hypoglycemic activity UV protector Neuroprotective properties

Olive stones

The olive stones are an important byproduct generated in the olive oil extraction. As a lignocellulosic material, the hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin are the main components of olive stones together with proteins, fats, phenols, free sugars and polyols. The main use of this biomass is combustion to produce electricity or heat. Other uses include synthesis of activated carbon, furfural production, plastic filled, abrasive and cosmetic or other potential uses such as biosorbent, animal feed or resin formation.²⁶ The chemical composition of olive whole stones and seed husks is reported in Table 13. Cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin are the main components of this lignocellulosic biomass, although fats and proteins are present in considerable quantities.

Table 13. Chemical composition of olive whole stones and olive seed husks (as % of dry weight).²⁶

Component	Whole stones	Seed husk
Moisture	9.79	9.98
Fat	5.53	1.01
Proteins	3.20	1.29
Free sugars	0.48	0.36
Neutral detergent fiber (NDF)	80.1	89.4
Acid detergent fiber (ADF)	58.2	62.6
Cellulose	31.9	36.4
Hemicellulose	21.9	26.8
Lignin	26.5	26.0

Tyrosol, hydroxytyrosol, oleuropein and diadehydric form of decarboxymethyl oleuropein (3,4 DHFEA-EDA) were present in all the olive tissues including the pulp, leaves, seed and stone.

Table 14. Range of phenols values in stone and seed olive for two seasons (phenols are expressed as grams per 100 g of dry matter).²⁶

Phenol	Stone	Seed
Tyrosol	0.1–0.8	0.5–4
Hydroxytyrosol	0.4–1.9	0.1–1
3,4 DHFEA-EDA	0.3–1.0	0.1–0.6
Oleuropein	0.1–0.2	0.1–0.2
Verbascoside	–	0.4–0.8
Nüzhenide	–	2.8–7.6

With an environmental and economic point of view, this byproduct can be considered to be a renewable energy source. In addition, further high added-value compounds may be obtained that may have other uses depending on specific chemical and physical properties. Table 13 outlines the most important uses of the whole stone or olive stone and other contributing factor.

Table 15. Present and future stone and seed uses.²⁶

Application	Raw material	Pretreatment	Raw transformed	Bases in properties	Application sector	Uses	Useful Byproduct and uses
Combustion	Stone and seed	Dried	Electric or heat	Physical (heat of combustion)	All industries residential and commercial	Nowadays in use	Ash/cement industries
Activated carbon	Stone and seed	Pyrolysis activation	Activated carbon	Physical (adsorption)	Food, chemical, petroleum, nuclear, mining, pharmacological industry	Nowadays in use	–
Bio-oil	Stone and seed	Pyrolysis	Liquid and gas production	Physical (combustion heat)	Wide field of industries	Nowadays in use	–
Olive seed oil	Seed	Separation extraction refining	Olive seed oil	Chemical	Food, pharmacological and cosmetic industry	Nowadays in use	–
Furfural	Stone and seed	Acid hydrolysis	Furfural	Chemical (Solvent)	Wide field of industries as solvent	Used in the past	Hydrolyzed/fertilizer
Plastic filled	Stone	Grinding	Composite	Physical	Plastic and construction	Nowadays in use	–
Abrasive	Stone	Grinding	Powder	Physical (hardness)	Cleaning	Nowadays in use	–
Cosmetic	Stone	Grinding	Cosmetic products	Physical (abrasive)	Cosmetic	Nowadays in use	–
Biosorbent	Stone	Grinding	Granulated or powder stone	Physical, chemical	Metallurgy and food	Potentially in use	–
Animal feed	Stone and seed	Grinding	Animal food	Physical	Food	Potentially in use	–
Resins	Stone and seed	Pyrolysis or liquefaction	Phenol–formaldehyde	Chemical	Electrochemical	Potentially in use	Fuel
Fractionation	Stone and seed	Steam explosion and fractionation	Soluble phenols and hemicellulose, lignin and cellulose	Chemical	Food, cosmetic, pharmaceutical, alcohol	Potentially in use	Source of protein and sugar/animal feed or fertilizer

Due to exfoliation qualities of olive stone, there are many market products that include this material as a component to aid in skin exfoliation.^{27,28} These products use an olive stone granules combine with hydrating components, and even heating agent.²⁹

Olive mill wastewater (OMWW)

Olive mill wastewater is the main liquid effluent obtained from the olive oil extraction. The worldwide annual production varies from 10 to more than 30 million m³, especially in the Mediterranean countries where the olive oil factories are omnipresent.³⁰ Olive mill wastewater is known by its strong unpleasant odor, the high number of phenolic compounds, total dissolved solids and a marked acidity.³¹ This by-product is known as the most harmful effluent from the olive oil factories because of its toxicity for the air, microorganisms, terrestrial and marine plants. Thus, the whole ecosystem could be highly infected by this waste.^{1,3} This toxicity is due to the high number of phenolic compounds.

According to the literature, the phenolic fraction of OMWW is divided into low and high molecular weight components.³² More than 50 phenolic compounds are already detected and quantified.³³ In the OMWW, a wide group's number of phenolic compounds groups was identified and quantified (Fig. 5-6). The group of benzoic (**1**) is composed by p-Hydroxybenzoic

(2), Protocatechuic (3), Vanillic (4), Veratric (5), Gallic (6) and Syringic acids (7). The Cinnamic acid (8) and derivatives is represented by p-Coumaric (9), Caffeic (10), Ferulic (11) and Synapic acids (12). As regard, Phenyl ethyl alcohol (13) and derivatives, we can cite tyrosol (14), and 3,4-dihydroxyphenylglycol (15), hydroxytyrosol (16). This latter, is the main phenolic component of the OMWW. The group of flavones (17) encloses Apigenin (18), Luteolin (19), Quercetin (20) and Rutin (21). Furthermore, Oleuropein (22) and Oleuropein aglycone (23) belonging to secoiridoids group are also detected in the OMWW composition. The group of phenol acids (24) and derivatives is also present in the OMWW composition, including p-Hydroxy phenyl acetic acid (25) and 3,4-Dihydroxyphenylglycol (26). Catechol was also identified in the OMWW composition (27)³⁴ Furthermore, Verbascoside (28) and its derivatives were also present in the composition of the OMWW. This includes Isoverbacoside (29), β -hydroxy verbascoside (30) and its diastereoisomer, β -hydroxy isoverbacoside (31) and its diastereoisomer, oxidized verbascoside (32) and oxidized Isoverbacoside (33).³⁴ In addition, other types of biophenols such as Luteolin-7-glucoside (34), Lutolin-7-rutinoside (35), Hydroxy tyrosol glucoside (36), Oleoside (37) and Pinoresinol (38) were also detected in the OMWW.³⁴

Figure 6. Phenolic compound fraction in OMWW.³⁴

Figure 7. Phenolic compound fraction in OMWW.³⁴

As previously reported, the major phenolic compounds identified in OMWW are oleuropein, hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol among others.³⁴ These biophenols possess a high spectrum of biological activities, including antiviral functions. Phenolic compounds and their secoiridoid derivatives present in OMWW are proven to inhibit or delay the rate of growth of a wide range of bacteria.³⁵ In general, the electron-donating and metal-chelating properties of phenolic compounds and their ability to delocalise the free radicals, make them potent antioxidants more than vitamins E and C on a molar basis.³⁶ Extraction methods and solvents used to obtain OMWW had a significant impact on the IC 50 values which could be related to the chemical composition of the evaluated extracts.³⁷

Galanakis et al.³⁸ investigated the application of different concentrations of phenols extracted from OMWW as UV booster in cosmetics. They proved that the absorption of synthetic UV filters increased as a function of olive phenols concentration in both UVB and UVA regions- Additionally, the cosmetic emulsions prepared using phenolic compounds entrapped in silica particles and/or liposomes have better water resistance.

C3. FRUIT PRODUCTION

C3.1 Introduction

In 2021 the overall fruits and vegetables production value of Basilicata was 411 millions euro, the main contribution of which was given by vegetables (230 millions), fruits (90 millions), followed by citrus fruits (35 millions). In 2020 the cultivated surface of Basilicata was c.a. 240000 ha (8000 ha of fruits and 14000 ha of vegetables) with a production of ca. 140000 tons of fruits, 215000 tons of vegetables, 100000 tons of citrus fruits (Table 2) (Annuario dell'Agricoltura Italiana 2020 – edizione LXXIV). The Metapontino area is the main site of agricultural production where is located the 75% of the overall regional production area, with 5000 companies in 74000 ha. Val d'Agri is known for late summer production, like beans and other vegetables that are high quality production among which there are many IGP products. In the Ofanto Vale the spreader species are tomatoes, salads, cabbage and fennel. The main planted fruits are apricot, peach and nectarine, oranges and mandarin, that have more economical profit. The tomatoes lead the industrial transformation followed by apricot, strawberries and citrus fruits.

Pomegranate

In the Basilicata region, approximately 10 ha of pomegranate (predominantly of the Wonderful variety) are cultivated, yielding a total production of 400 tons. About 20% of the pomegranates are discarded during the harvest, while for pomegranate juice production, the amount of waste can reach up to 80% of the pomegranate's weight. The pomegranates have been regarded as a medicinal food of great importance for therapeutic purposes against stomach ailments,^{1,2} they are also known for their anti-inflammatory and anti-atherosclerotic effect activity against osteoarthritis, prostate cancer, heart disease, and HIV-1.^{3,4} The juice from pomegranates is one of nature's most powerful antioxidants as it has 3 times higher antioxidant activity than those of red wine and green tea.⁵ Pomegranate anthocyanins have scavenging activities, while its polyphenolic compounds elevate the antioxidant capacity of the human body.^{6,7} All parts of the pomegranate tree including the roots, the reddish-brown bark, leaves, flowers, rinds, and seeds, have been used in medicine for thousands of years as they are rich sources of various chemical constituents (Table 14).⁶

Table 16. Chemical Constituents of Different Parts of Pomegranate Plant.⁶

Compound	material
Anthocyanins, glucose, ascorbic acid, ellagic acid, gallic acid, caffeic acid, catechin, Minerals, amino acids, quercetin, rutin	Pomegranate Juice
95% punicic acid, ellagic acid, sterols	Pomegranate seed oil
Phenolic punicalagins, gallic acid, catechin, flavones, flavonones, anthocyanidins	Pomegranate pericarp (peel, rind)
Tannins, flavone glycosides, luteolin, apigenin	Pomegranate leaves
Gallic acid, ursolic acid, triterpenoids including maslinic, and asiatic acid	Pomegranate flower
Ellagitannins, punicalin and punicalagin, piperidine alkaloids	Pomegranate roots and bark

Table 17. Total Polyphenols, Flavonoids, Anthocyanins, and Hydrolysable Tannins Contents of Pomegranate Peels and Seeds.^{8,9}

By-product	Total polyphenol (mg/g GAE, db) ^a		Total flavonoids (mg/g RE, db) ^b		Total anthocyanins (mg/g CGE, db) ^c		Hydrolysable tannins (mg/g TAE, db) ^d	
	Water	Methanol	Water	Methanol	Water	Methanol	Water	Methanol
Peel	53.65	85.60	21.03	51.52	51.02	102.2	62.71	139.63
Seed	7.94	11.84	3.30	6.79	19.62	40.84	32.86	29.57

^amg gallic acid equivalents per g dry weight.

^bmg tannic acid equivalents per g of dry weight.

^cmg rutin equivalents per g dry weight.

^dmg cyanidin-3-glucoside equivalents per g dry weight.

Teh¹⁰ studied the compositions of the juice, peel, and seed of five pomegranate varieties grown in California and reported that the pomegranate fruits contain 38%–50% juice, 39%–53% peel, and 8%–12% seed (Fig. 7). Pomegranate juice is also used to provide color to other products. It is a rich source of polyphenols. The phenolic constituents, such as anthocyanins, give the color. Flavonoids and some nonflavonoids are responsible for antioxidant properties, astringency, and bitterness of the juice.⁵ The high antioxidant content of pomegranate juice makes it suitable for production of health supplements and nutraceuticals.¹¹

Means with the same letters are not significantly different ($P < .01$).

Figure 8. Composition of pomegranate fruits of five varieties.¹¹

Strawberry

In Basilicata strawberry production occurs in greenhouses over 38589 ha with an overall production of 121048 q (chart 7), mainly located in the Metapontino area, representing the 22% of the regional PIL with the overall commercial value of 100 million euro.¹²

We contacted Apofruit company, one of the major player in the strawberry fruits production in Basilicata which informed us that, in general, only 10% of the fruits goes to industry transformation, while most of the production is directly delivered to the market. The majority of waste derives from the plant residues (leaves, root) that offers new opportunity to extract byproducts to be implemented in cosmetic or pharma industry.¹³ Strawberry leaves are mainly composed of polyphenols recognized for their antioxidant capacities and benefits on human health, from anti-aging properties to cancer treatment.¹⁴ The most interesting compounds considered in this study due to the quantity present in strawberry plants were ellagic acid, ascorbic acid, and agrimoniin. The ellagic acid derivatives have the potential to protect the skin from oxidative stress and pollution and boost the production of collagen fibers. The ellagic acid quantity related to the leaves is 112.7 mg per 100 grams of fresh material.¹⁵ In addition, ascorbic acid is known for antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and UV protection. The presence of vitamin C is 138.08 mg per 100 grams of fresh leaves weight.¹⁶ Finally, agrimoniin is the main compound found in the leaves, with almost 35 % wt., having antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities acting against UVB-induced inflammation.¹⁷ Agrimoniin quantities are 498.4 mg per 100 grams of fresh material.¹⁴ The extract composition could vary with the source of the raw material due to environmental facts such as weather, soil nutrients, water availability, etc.¹⁸ Strawberry fruits have been studied in the past years founded reach of many important molecules with many properties, summarized in Table 18. Those reported represent the most common components found among *Fragaria L.* species and can be vary throughout other species and can be influenced by many factors, like seasonal harvest, climate and more.

Table 18. Major (common) components in *Fragaria L.* aggregate fruits.¹⁹

Class	Compound
Anthocyanins	Pelargonidin 3-glucoside, cyanidin 3-glucoside, cyanidin 3-rutinoside, pelargonidin 3-galactoside, pelargonidin 3-rutinoside, pelargonidin 3-arabinoside, pelargonidin 3-malylglucoside
Flavonols	Quercetin, kaempferol, fisetin, their glucuronides, and glycosides
Flavanols	Catechin, proanthocyanidin B1, proanthocyanidin trimer, proanthocyanidin B3
Ellagitannins	Sanguin H-6, ellagitannin, ellagic acid, lambertianin C, galloylbis-hexahydroxydiphenoyl-glucose
Phenolic acids	4-coumaric acid, p-hydroxybenzoic acid, ferulic acid, vanillic acid, sinapic acid
Vitamins	Vitamin C, vitamin B9
Minerals	Mn, K, mg, P, Ca
Others	Sugars (glucose, fructose, and sucrose), fibers

C4. NUTS PRODUCTION

C3.1 Introduction

Cultivation of walnuts and chestnuts are traditionally well developed in Basilicata, especially chestnuts in the mountainous north-eastern part of the Vulture Melfese area. More recently, the cultivation of hazelnuts and pistachios have been greatly developed.

In particular, the hazelnuts cultivation had a very high increase after the creation of the regional Consortium “Basilicata in guscio”, which promotes creation of novel hazelnuts cultivations supporting the farmers from the choice of the suitable terrain to the cultivation technique and, finally, to the commercialization of the product. The Consortium signed an agreement with the famous Ferrero company to supply fixed amounts of the hazelnuts production at fixed prices. The number of hazelnut producers has grown up to 65 companies while the orchard area, including both that already under production and that implanted is of 424 ha.

A great development has been also recently observed in the pistachio production, essentially in the area of Stigliano, in the province of Matera. Here the high quality DOP “Pistacchio di Stigliano” is produced. Nowadays the total extension of pistachio orchards reaches 30 ha, one of the largest single orchard in Italy for a 53 q production.

Pistachio

A recent study,²⁰ focused on the valorization of the stalks of pistachio cultivation that otherwise is treated as a waste material. The stalks have been steam treated and the extract have been analyzed founded data reported in Table 17.²⁰ Fourteen compounds were identified by comparing the m/z values in the total ion current (TIC) and the fragmentation patterns with those described in the literature.²¹ The nanoformulations, especially transfersomes developed for the *P. vera* extracts, especially the essential oil, hold promise for the modulation of the function of activated macrophages, which play a key role in responding to inflammation and initiating wound healing.

Table 19. Metabolites identified in *P. vera* essential oil via LC-ESI/Orbitrap/MS/MS (positive mode).

Peak No.	Compound	Rt (min)	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight	[M+H] ⁺	Δ Ppm	MS/MS
1	Vanillic acid	2.06	C ₈ H ₈ O ₄	168.18	169	0.18	142, 97
2	<i>p</i> -coumaric acid	2.52	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃	164.05	165	-0.31	147, 82
3	Sinapinic acid	3.60	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₅	224.07	225	0.71	207
4	Myristic acid	3.73	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	228.21	229	-0.21	225, 191
5	Caffeic acid	14.57	C ₉ H ₈ O ₄	180.04	181	0.41	181, 163
6	Catechin	16.95	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	290.08	291	0.38	245, 151, 109
7	α-pinene	17.49	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136.24	137	0.24	109, 95, 81
8	Ascorbic acid	17.96	C ₆ H ₈ O ₆	176.04	177	-0.43	177, 159
9	Tryptophan	17.99	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	204.09	205	0.39	205, 144
10	Naringenin	18.36	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₅	272.07	273	0.57	255, 244, 95
11	Cinnamic acid	18.41	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂	148.05	149	-0.34	131, 121, 65
12	Luteolin	18.83	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	286.24	287	0.24	269, 243, 135
13	Ferulic acid	20.33	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄	194.06	195	-0.26	177
14	Tyrosine	26.88	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO ₃	181.07	182	0.36	182, 165, 136

C) CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of the waste production from the agricultural activities in Basilicata has been carried out by resorting to available databases of national and/or regional statistical research institutes like ISTAT, CREA, SIAN and integrated of the missing data by administering specific surveys to the agricultural enterprises within the region Basilicata. The study was completed with data on the bioactive compounds content of the waste biomass.

On the basis of the available data it was possible to select the waste biomass most suitable for valorization, taking into account their availability, the environmental problems connected to their disposal, their potential for valorization depending on the valuable metabolites content.

Such analysis prompted us to select the waste coming from wine production (grape pomace, grape lees and grape stalks), those coming from olive oil production (olive pomace, mill waste water, olive stones), those coming from pomegranate orchard (peel and seeds) and those from pistachio production, as the most promising for valorization and recovery of valuable by-products for application on cosmetics/nutraceuticals.

The RM7 partners already started an investigation on the metabolite content of such waste biomasses and on the sustainable processes for the recovery of such compounds.

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E) ANNEXES

ANNEX 1: Examples of data collection from available national and regional agriculture databases.

	N. Dich. e alleg. F2	TOTALE				Uva per vino				Uva per vino con indicazione della varietà				Uva per vino IGP				Uva per vino DOP			
		Sup. (ha)	Nera (Q.li)	Bianca (Q.li)	Totale (Q.li)	Sup. (ha)	Nera (Q.li)	Bianca (Q.li)	Totale (Q.li)	Sup. (ha)	Nera (Q.li)	Bianca (Q.li)	Totale (Q.li)	Sup. (ha)	Nera (Q.li)	Bianca (Q.li)	Totale (Q.li)	Sup. (ha)	Nera (Q.li)	Bianca (Q.li)	Totale (Q.li)
ABRUZZO	7.223	23.798	2.290.222	1.985.798	4.276.020	6.855	740.762	1.063.899	1.804.661	487	36.058	77.742	113.800	3.887	168.934	595.674	764.608	12.569	1.344.469	248.483	1.592.952
BASILICATA	751	1.921	135.090	37.742	172.832	724	52.683	15.741	68.424	0	0	0	0	497	29.107	21.067	50.174	700	53.300	934	54.234

Figure 1. Crop data of grapes year 2022 from SIAN (Sistema Informativo Agricolo Nazionale).

Regione	Codice	Denominazione	Rivendicazioni (numero)	Uva rivendicata (q.li)	Uva da supero (q.li)	Superficie (ha)	Vino ottenibile (hl)
BASILICATA	B080	AGLIANICO DEL VULTURE		233	43,006.38	536.15	30,104.49
BASILICATA	A049	AGLIANICO DEL VULTURE SUPERIORE		48	5,471.54	80.31	3,556.52
BASILICATA	B401	GROTTINO DI ROCCANOVA		16	771.52	12.06	540.06
BASILICATA	B379	MATERA		40	3,959.17	56.43	2,771.87
BASILICATA	B367	TERRE DELL'ALTA VAL D'AGRI		6	1,038.60	15.99	727.02

TOTALE BASILICATA	343	54,247.21	700.94	37,699.96
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Chart A1.1 Wine production year 2022, SIAN.

Dataset: Coltivazioni

Selezione periodo	Territorio Basilicata									
	2022					2023				
Tipo dato	superficie totale - ettari	superficie in produzione - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione totale - ettolitri	produzione raccolta - quintali	superficie totale - ettari	superficie in produzione - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione totale - ettolitri	produzione raccolta - quintali
Tipo di coltivazione										
uva da vino	2027	1980	182278	..	155419	2024	1952	106591	..	106004
uve per vini dop	882	869	47792	..	47305	847	846	43272	..	43280
uve per vini igp	360	355	37488	..	37166	370	365	37218	..	37170
uve per altri vini (escluso dop e igp)	985	956	96998	..	70948	989	967	96922	..	66424
vino	86187	79770	..
vino da tavola	32903	32275	..
vino bianco da tavola	3808	4537	..
vino rosso e rosato da tavola	29095	27738	..
vino D.O.P:	27260	32026	..
vino D.O.P: bianco	499	388	..
vino D.O.P: rosso e rosato	26761	31638	..
vino I.G.P.	26024	26370	..
vino I.G.P. bianco	11197	13166	..
vino I.G.P. rosso e rosato	14827	13204	..
uva da tavola	489	485	124228	..	123471	513	506	108174	..	107822
olive da tavola e da olio	26086	25985	307357	..	290794	27610	27470	325331	..	322444
olive da tavola	185	158	960	..	930	173	170	885	..	844
altre olive	25921	25827	306397	..	289864	27437	27300	324446	..	321600
olive da olio	25921	25827	306397	..	289864	27437	27300	324446	..	321600
olio di oliva	53297	57549

Dati estratti il 05 feb 2024 14:56 UTC (GMT) da I.Stat

Chart A1.2. Grape, wine, olive and oil production in Basilicata, year 2022 and 2023, ISTAT.

Dataset:Coltivazioni

Territorio	Basilicata								
Selezione periodo	2022			2023			2024		
Tipo dato	superficie totale - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione raccolta - quintali	superficie totale - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione raccolta - quintali	superficie totale - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione raccolta - quintali
Tipo di coltivazione									
ortive
pisello fresco
altri legumi freschi
fava fresca in piena aria
altri legumi freschi diversi dalla fava
legumi freschi
aglio e scalogno in piena aria
porro in piena aria
cavolo di bruxelles	30	6263	6250	30	6385	6347
cavolo bianco
cavolo rosso
cavolo verza	168	37597	37241	164	36514	36368
broccoletto di rapa in piena aria	608	77927	76218	600	78300	77875
altri cavoli diversi dai broccoletti di rapa	223	42485	42319
cavolfiore (e cavolo broccolo)	1141	222205	221416	1128	220499	219091
pomodoro
pomodoro da consumo fresco in serra
pomodoro da trasformazione in serra
ortive in piena aria
pisello in piena aria	70	3049	3048	70	3049	3048
fagiolo e fagiolino in piena aria	212	15114	14967	212	15114	14967
cipolla in piena aria	23	3896	3890	23	3896	3890
scalogno in piena aria
carota e pastinaca in piena aria	249	47915	47766
rapa in piena aria
barbabietola da orto in piena aria
asparago in piena aria	72	4477	4410	72	4477	4410
radicchio o cicoria in piena aria	173	38857	38147
sedano in piena aria	157	60447	59947
cavolo cappuccio in piena aria
carciofo in piena aria	430	52625	52305	430	52625	52305	426	53588	53560
melanzana in piena aria	324	69190	69132	324	69190	69132
peperone in piena aria	518	105263	96066	518	105263	96066
cetriolo da mensa in piena aria
cetriolo da sottaceti in piena aria
lattuga in piena aria	532	115515	114565
popone o melone in piena aria	697	143372	143360	697	143372	143360
zucchina in piena aria	164	22317	20179	164	22317	20179
cocomero in piena aria	221	103382	87150	221	103382	87150
finocchio in piena aria	793	199356	198394
indivia (riccia e scarola) in piena aria	378	84323	84154
ravanello in piena aria
spinacio in piena aria
bietola da costa in piena aria	113	21876	21755
altri cavoli in piena aria
pomodoro in piena aria
aglio
altre verdure a foglia o a stelo diverse dalla bietola da costa
pomodoro da consumo fresco o da mensa	884	366001	365454	884	366001	365454
pomodoro da trasformazione in piena aria	2083	1160563	1152725	2083	1160563	1152725

Chart A1.3. Vegetables crops production in Basilicata, ISTAT.

TAB. 10.1 - AZIENDE AGRICOLE E SUPERFICI A VITE PER VINI DOP E IGP, 2020

	Aziende con vite per DOP-IGP (n.)	Aziende con vite per la produzione di altri vini (n.)	Superfici a vite DOP-IGP (ha)	Superfici a vite per la produzione di altri vini (ha)
Piemonte	8.810	4.311	39.334	3.254
Valle d'Aosta	409	232	362	57
Lombardia	4.196	1.605	23.055	1.395
Bolzano	3.384	396	5.372	193
Trento	5.449	644	10.512	346
Veneto	18.743	7.695	89.986	10.340
Friuli Venezia Giulia	2.832	1.798	23.597	2.123
Liguria	856	1.124	966	356
Emilia-Romagna	8.622	7.417	36.504	17.521
Toscana	7.283	8.080	51.273	5.979
Umbria	1.440	5.349	6.407	2.693
Marche	2.177	6.240	10.851	3.060
Lazio	2.688	8.173	10.141	5.000
Abruzzo	7.079	7.011	21.644	7.342
Molise	264	3.383	934	2.705
Campania	6.004	15.117	11.506	9.659
Puglia	11.146	19.635	31.818	39.519
Basilicata	803	4.323	1.662	1.624
Calabria	1.313	7.237	3.234	3.313
Sicilia	15.273	11.246	64.756	12.754
Sardegna	2.985	7.927	9.035	7.388
Italia	111.756	128.943	452.949	136.621

Fonte: 7° Censimento generale dell'agricoltura, 2020.

Chart A1.4. Grapes production for DOP and IGP wine, year 2020, from CREA report.

	Basilicata	
	superficie	produzione
CEREALI		
Fumento duro	115.160	287.900
Fumento tenero	6.952	20.856
Mais	821	3.846
INDUSTRIALI		
Colza	541	577
Girasole	49	59
Soia	-	-
OLIVE		
Totale olive	26.086	30.736
UVA		
Uva da tavola	489	12.423
Uva da vino	2.027	18.228
FRUTTA		
Kiwi	-	-
Albicocca	3.765	43.737
ciliegia	66	375
Mela	-	-
Nettarina (pesca noce)	1.011	24.126
Nocciola	45	77
Pero	-	-
Pesco	1.862	34.570
ORTAGGI (in piena aria)		
Carciofo	430	5.263
Cavolfiore e cavolo broccolo	1.141	22.221
Indivia (riccia e scarola)	-	-
Radicchio o cicoria	-	-
Patata comune	105	1.985
Peperone	518	10.526
Pomodoro	884	36.600
Pomodoro da industria	2.083	116.056
ORTAGGI E FRUTTA (in serra)		
Fragola	-	-
Lattuga	-	-
Melanzana	-	-
Peperone	-	-
Pomodoro	-	-
Melone	-	-
Zucchina	-	-
AGRUMI		
Arancio	3.834	70.114
Clementina	1.275	19.388
Limone	49	992
Mandarino	656	10.040

Chart A1.5. Istat data production.

TAB. A6 - PRODUZIONE AI PREZZI DI BASE DELL'AGRICOLTURA PER REGIONE E PRINCIPALI PRODOTTI

(quantità: migliaia di tonnellate; valori: migliaia di euro)

	Italia			
	2021		2022	
	quantità	valore	quantità	valore
Prodotti delle coltivazioni arboree				
Uva conferita e venduta	3.852,0	1.439.887	3.984,8	1.511.225
Uva da tavola	1.014,8	709.490	961,7	614.540
Uva da vino p.c.d.	29,5	10.408	29,1	10.449
Olive vendute e p.c.d.	271,6	289.529	247,8	261.942
Arance	1.770,9	654.313	1.776,3	649.609
Mandarini	148,7	47.296	132,3	45.058
Clementine	673,4	184.955	652,3	202.520
Limoni	466,3	393.960	447,7	586.033
Bergamotti	26,9	8.525	26,5	9.557
Cedri	1,1	894	1,1	1.023
Pompelmi	5,5	4.052	5,3	4.455
Mele	2.211,8	926.687	2.313,6	1.089.336
Pere	273,4	427.259	493,9	500.804
Pesche	718,4	329.013	772,2	352.920
Nettarine	278,6	204.066	379,0	296.402
Albicocche	189,4	122.729	230,0	137.198
Ciliege	93,4	129.113	109,0	133.279
Susine	137,7	67.275	187,2	104.034
Cotogne	0,8	261	0,8	284
Melograni	18,5	5.908	25,4	8.817
Fichi freschi	12,8	16.915	12,9	18.087
Loti	45,4	18.367	52,1	22.871
Mandorle	71,5	80.435	74,4	81.365
Nocciole	84,7	193.320	98,8	199.781
Noci	6,4	18.297	6,9	21.467
Carrube	37,7	2.992	35,6	2.596
Actinidia	416,0	327.981	537,3	465.898
Fichi secchi	1,5	2.730	1,4	2.342
Prugne secche	1,5	2.904	1,5	2.669
Altre legnose a frutto annuo	4,0	2.520	3,8	2.526
Prodotti trasformati				
Vino (000 hl)	22.751,0	4.161.192	22.783,0	4.593.935
Vinacce	125,3	5.170	125,2	5.328
Cremor tartaro	2,3	1.938	2,3	2.025
Olio	304,1	1.451.720	250,0	1.293.772
Sanse	469,8	12.859	386,3	10.903
Altre legnose				
Canne e vimini	21,4	2.109	20,7	2.226
Vivai	-	1.505.541	-	1.677.525
Prodotti degli allevamenti¹				
Bovini	1.171,2	2.977.100	1.200,3	3.645.882
Equini	39,6	99.937	39,4	108.368
Suini	2.100,0	3.052.185	2.041,4	3.512.771
Ovini e caprini	57,4	167.273	57,3	184.654
Pollame	1.912,7	2.926.949	1.884,3	3.846.541
Conigli, selvaggina e allevamenti minori	261,0	722.007	256,0	814.359
Latte di vacca e bufala (000 hl)	127.220,0	4.880.096	126.585,0	6.238.712
Latte di pecora e capra (000 hl)	6.194,0	572.330	6.182,0	629.824
Uova (milioni di pezzi)	12.725,0	1.456.354	12.674,0	1.850.677
Miele	2,5	27.587	2,3	29.424
Cera	0,08	1.003	0,1	963
Bozzoli	0,03	293	0,0	325
Lana	5,0	7.288	5,0	7.809

Chart A1.6. Istat data production of pomace and tartar

	Italia	
	superficie	produzione
CEREALI		
Frumento duro	1.237.958	3.740.765
Frumento tenero	538.771	2.776.794
Mais	563.704	4.717.454
INDUSTRIALI		
Colza	18.514	53.159
Girasole	110.818	265.661
Soia	342.532	918.068
OLIVE		
Totale olive	1.122.456	2.261.325
UVA		
Uva da tavola	47.583	1.010.398
Uva da vino	684.532	7.512.473
FRUTTA		
Kiwi	25.618	532.374
Albicocca	18.308	236.910
ciliegia	29.279	113.611
Mela	56.234	2.279.127
Nettarina (pesca noce)	18.115	387.216
Nocciola	94.529	104.879
Pero	25.989	527.167
Pesco	40.187	794.036
ORTAGGI (in piena aria)		
Carciofo	38.166	385.807
Cavolfiore e cavolo broccolo	14.728	359.289
Indivia (riccia e scarola)	6.684	147.938
Radicchio o cicoria	8.190	164.381
Patata comune	33.057	1.035.632
Peperone	7.803	169.557
Pomodoro	16.754	501.325
Pomodoro da industria	74.041	5.211.513
ORTAGGI E FRUTTA (in serra)		
Fragola	206.480	71.181
Lattuga	551.802	202.283
Melanzana	149.252	86.672
Peperone	159.002	68.895
Pomodoro	681.617	490.373
Melone	236.792	82.154
Zucchina	363.344	196.703
AGRUMI		
Arancio	85.472	1.816.536
Clementina	26.188	656.840
Limone	26.211	482.293
Mandarino	8.786	156.893

Chart A1.7. Istat data production. *produzione in tonnellate

	Basilicata				
	2021	2022	var. % 2022/21		
			valore	volume	prezzo
COLTIVAZIONI AGRICOLE	607.566	735.015	21,0	-2,7	24,4
Coltivazioni erbacee	426.887	549.911	28,8	-3,3	33,2
Cereali	194.865	233.449	19,8	-9,7	32,6
Legumi secchi	2.107	2.456	16,5	-	16,5
Patate e ortaggi	229.004	312.968	36,7	2,1	33,8
Industriali	215	250	16,5	-	16,5
Fiori e piante da vaso	697	788	13,1	2,0	10,9
Coltivazioni foraggere	14.775	20.219	36,8	-2,5	40,4
Coltivazioni legnose	165.904	164.885	-0,6	-1,4	0,8
Prodotti vitivinicoli	21.730	23.980	10,4	0,9	9,4
Prodotti dell'olivicultura	15.802	12.599	-20,3	-25,1	6,4
Agrumi	34.570	37.429	8,3	4,9	3,2
Frutta	90.469	87.139	-3,7	-0,4	-3,3
Altre legnose	3.333	3.739	12,2	1,6	10,4
ALLEVAMENTI ZOOTECNICI	169.108	200.314	18,5	-1,4	20,1
Prodotti zootecnici alimentari	168.354	199.509	18,5	-1,4	20,2
Carni	130.112	153.671	18,1	-0,9	19,2
Latte	27.720	33.953	22,5	-0,3	22,8
Uova	8.310	10.603	27,6	-	27,6
Miele	2.213	1.283	-42,0	-50,0	16,0
Prodotti zootecnici non alimentari	753	804	6,8	-1,6	8,5
ATTIVITÀ DI SUPPORTO ALL'AGRICOLTURA	247.962	273.458	10,3	-7,3	19,0
Produzione di beni e servizi dell'agricoltura	1.024.636	1.208.787	18,0	-3,6	22,4
(+) Attività secondarie ²	52.937	70.797	33,7	13,7	17,7
(-) Attività secondarie ²	24.391	32.978	35,2	-7,3	45,9
Produzione della branca agricoltura	1.053.182	1.246.606	18,4	-2,7	21,6

Chart A1.8. CREA data for 2022 regarding the Basilicata region, highlighting wine and olive cultivation products (Source: ISTAT <https://esploradati.istat.it>). The data is reported in thousands of euros.

PRODUZIONE AI PREZZI DI BASE DELL'AGRICOLTURA

(quantità: migliaia di tonnellate; valori: migliaia di euro)

	Basilicata			
	2021		2022	
	quantità	valore	quantità	valore
Prodotti delle coltivazioni arboree				
Uva conferita e venduta	0,8	230	0,7	198
Uva da tavola	12,3	8.613	10,8	6.912
Uva da vino p.c.d.	-	-	-	-
Olive vendute e p.c.d.	3,2	2.250	2,9	2.012
Arance	69,1	25.380	75,7	27.526
Mandarini	9,8	3.115	6,4	2.177
Clementine	19,3	5.192	20,0	6.085
Limoni	1,0	883	1,2	1.641
Bergamotti	-	-	-	-
Cedri	-	-	-	-
Pompelmi	-	-	-	-
Mele	8,4	3.625	9,3	4.511
Pere	7,3	11.889	6,8	7.287
Pesche	33,6	15.747	33,6	15.731
Nettarine	24,1	18.149	24,1	19.474
Albicocche	43,3	27.998	43,3	25.758
Ciliege	0,4	550	0,4	486
Susine	9,1	4.507	9,1	5.125
Cotogne	-	-	-	-
Melograni	-	-	-	-
Fichi freschi	-	-	-	-
Loti	-	-	-	-
Mandorle	0,4	450	0,4	438
Nocciole	0,1	228	0,1	202
Noci	-	-	-	-
Carrube	-	-	-	-
Actinidia	7,6	6.005	7,9	6.866
Fichi secchi	-	-	-	-
Prugne secche	-	-	-	-
Altre legnose a frutto annuo	-	-	-	-
Prodotti trasformati				
Vino (000 hl) ²	121,0	12.857	133,0	16.838
Vinacce	-	-	-	-
Cremor tartaro	-	-	-	-
Olio	4,7	13.351	3,4	10.437
Sanse	-	-	-	-

Chart A1.9. the ISTAT data extrapolated for the year 2022 for the Basilicata region regarding the overall production of Oil and Wine (quantity expressed in thousands of tonnes, value expressed in thousands of euros)

Segue **TAB. A5 - PRODUZIONE AI PREZZI DI BASE DELL'AGRICOLTURA PER TIPO DI PRODOTTO¹**

(migliaia di euro)

	Basilicata					Calabria				
	2020	2021	var. % 2021/20			2020	2021	var. % 2021/20		
			valore	volume	prezzo			valore	volume	prezzo
Coltivazioni agricole	538.388	595.911	10,7	-2,0	13,0	1.478.654	1.613.635	9,1	3,7	5,3
Coltivazioni erbacee	369.851	420.406	13,7	-2,3	16,4	636.793	636.944	0,0	-3,3	3,4
Cereali	146.533	191.434	30,6	-2,6	34,1	48.201	61.175	26,9	-3,8	31,9
Legumi secchi	1.918	2.114	10,2	0,0	10,2	4.560	4.720	3,5	-6,2	10,4
Patate e ortaggi	220.605	225.959	2,4	-2,2	4,8	579.809	566.594	-2,3	-3,3	1,0
Industriali	151	216	43,1	0,0	43,1	67	98	45,9	6,9	36,5
Fiori e piante da vaso	644	683	6,1	4,1	2,0	4.157	4.357	4,8	2,8	2,0
Coltivazioni foraggere	12.254	14.363	17,2	-0,5	17,8	15.942	18.579	16,5	-1,1	17,8
Coltivazioni legnose	156.284	161.142	3,1	-1,4	4,5	825.918	958.113	16,0	9,1	6,3
Prodotti vitivinicoli	19.550	21.746	11,2	6,1	4,8	94.533	94.914	0,4	-0,6	1,0
Prodotti dell'olivicoltura	13.153	15.783	20,0	11,5	7,7	335.323	407.914	21,6	9,9	10,7
Agrumi	32.210	30.692	-4,7	-9,9	5,7	278.773	334.701	20,1	15,2	4,2
Frutta	88.253	89.632	1,6	-2,0	3,6	107.507	110.385	2,7	0,1	2,6
Altre legnose	3.118	3.288	5,5	3,4	2,0	9.783	10.199	4,2	2,2	2,0
Allevamenti zootecnici	159.980	169.108	5,7	0,6	5,0	241.559	253.129	4,8	1,0	3,8
Prodotti zootecnici alimentari	159.061	168.354	5,8	0,8	5,0	240.771	252.513	4,9	1,0	3,8
Carni	120.201	130.112	8,2	2,4	5,7	154.976	166.846	7,7	2,2	5,3
Latte	25.837	27.720	7,3	4,1	3,1	46.998	49.862	6,1	3,0	3,0
Uova	8.336	8.310	-0,3	1,6	-1,9	35.959	35.805	-0,4	1,5	-1,9
Miele	4.688	2.213	-52,8	-60,0	18,0	2.838	-	-	-	-
Prodotti zootecnici non alimentari	919	753	-18,0	-20,9	3,6	788	616	-21,8	-24,5	3,6
Attività di supporto all'agricoltura	236.011	247.962	5,1	3,3	1,7	318.277	338.340	6,3	3,9	2,3
Produzione di beni e servizi dell'agricoltura	934.380	1.012.980	8,4	-0,2	8,7	2.038.490	2.205.104	8,2	3,4	4,6
(+) Attività secondarie ²	47.744	55.276	15,8	-1,3	17,2	117.343	136.128	16,0	4,4	11,1
(-) Attività secondarie ²	23.696	24.391	2,9	-23,0	33,6	59.528	59.029	-0,8	-22,0	27,1
Produzione della branca agricoltura	958.428	1.043.865	8,9	0,3	8,6	2.096.305	2.282.203	8,9	4,1	4,5

1. Le variazioni di valore sono calcolate con valori correnti, le variazioni di volume sono calcolate con valori concatenati con anno base 2015, le variazioni di prezzo sono calcolate come differenza tra la variazione di valore e quella di volume.

2. Per attività secondaria va intesa sia quella effettuata nell'ambito della branca di attività agricola e quindi non separabile, vale a dire agriturismo, trasformazione del latte, frutta e carne, evidenziata con il segno (+), sia quella esercitata da altre branche d'attività economica nell'ambito delle coltivazioni e degli allevamenti (per esempio da imprese commerciali), evidenziata con il segno (-).

Chart A1.10. Some general crop data from CREA report.

Segue TAB. A6 - PRODUZIONE AI PREZZI DI BASE DELL'AGRICOLTURA PER REGIONE E PRINCIPALI PRODOTTI¹

(quantità: migliaia di tonnellate; valori: migliaia di euro)

	Basilicata				Calabria			
	2020		2021		2020		2021	
	quantità	valore	quantità	valore	quantità	valore	quantità	valore
Prodotti delle coltivazioni erbacee								
Cereali								
Frumento tenero	18,7	3.545	-	-	29,9	5.849	27,5	6.800
Frumento duro	324,8	124.415	324,8	168.184	65,2	23.130	61,1	29.301
Segale	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Orzo	41,1	6.024	41,1	7.945	21,3	3.426	21,7	4.604
Avena	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Riso	-	-	-	-	2,6	584	2,4	553
Granoturco nostrano	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Granoturco ibrido (mais)	3,8	725	3,8	1.011	18,1	3.479	18,4	4.930
Cereali minori	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Paglie	152,9	3.644	144,9	4.069	47,1	1.122	45,0	1.263
Leguminose da granella								
Fave secche	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fagioli secchi	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Piselli secchi	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ceci	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lenticchie	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lupini	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Veccia	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Patate e ortaggi								
Patate	2,0	975	2,0	966	132,8	69.545	132,0	69.097
Fave fresche	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fagioli freschi	1,5	2.438	1,5	2.269	13,5	22.154	11,7	17.867
Piselli freschi	0,3	220	0,3	237	2,2	1.617	1,9	1.503
Pomodori	153,4	19.679	153,4	18.923	165,8	25.361	160,7	23.898
Cardi	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Finocchi	21,0	38.491	19,8	35.093	111,0	204.909	109,2	194.934
Sedani	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cavoli	23,3	12.944	27,7	17.358	52,7	29.211	53,0	33.138
Cavolfiori	22,1	15.155	21,9	16.460	25,3	17.217	26,0	19.392
Cipolle	0,4	243	0,4	274	38	23.252	37,9	26.182
Agli	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Melone	20,9	30.189	21,0	33.749	23,7	8.678	24,2	7.444
Cocomeri	8,7	1.773	8,7	1.589	3,3	681	3,0	554
Asparagi	0,4	827	0,4	742	0,2	413	0,2	370
Carciofi	5,2	8.111	5,2	8.093	3,0	4.666	3,0	4.656
Rape	3,4	928	3,2	907	4,9	1.348	4,7	1.342
Barbabietole da orto	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Carote	4,5	2.501	4,8	2.865	0,4	222	0,4	239
Spinaci	-	-	-	-	0,4	275	0,4	322
Cetrioli	0,2	74	0,2	81	5,0	3.882	5,1	4.328
Fragole	12,1	36.642	10,5	36.535	10,2	24.476	8,7	23.286
Melanzane	6,9	3.527	6,9	2.735	25	13.181	23,7	9.945
Peperoni	9,6	9.984	9,6	10.753	24,7	26.200	23,6	26.992
Zucchine	2,0	1.241	2,0	1.428	41,8	29.216	37,8	30.099
Zucche	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Indivia	9,0	5.286	8,4	5.358	3,5	2.024	2,9	1.822
Lattuga	12,4	9.152	11,6	7.744	17,3	15.921	15,7	14.222
Radicchio	3,7	1.731	3,8	1.931	0,7	333	0,1	52
Bietole	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Orti familiari	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Piante industriali								
Barbabietola da zucchero	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tabacco	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Canapa Tiglio	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lino seme	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cotone fibra	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cotone seme	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Colza	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ravizzone	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Arachide	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Girasole	0,1	23	0,1	29	0,1	23	0,1	29
Sesamo	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Soia	-	-	-	-	0,1	30	0,1	45
Altre, comprese le spontanee	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Foraggi (in fieno)	-	12.254	-	14.363	-	15.942	-	18.579
Fiori e piante ornamentali	-	644	-	683	-	4.157	-	4.357

Chart A1.11. General crop data from CREA report.

Dataset:Coltivazioni											
Territorio Basilicata											
Selezione periodo											
2022											
2023											
2024											
Tipo dato	superficie totale - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione raccolta - quintali	superficie totale - ettari	superficie totale - are	produzione totale - quintali	produzione raccolta - quintali	superficie totale - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione raccolta - quintali	
Tipo di coltivazione											
ortive
fragola in piena aria
fragola in serra
						38589	121048	120556			

Dati estratti il 12 giu 2024, 09h22 UTC (GMT) da I.Stat

Chart A1.12. Strawberry production of Basilicata, data source ISTAT.

Territorio Basilicata									
Selezione periodo									
2022									
2023									
Tipo dato	superficie totale - ettari	superficie in produzione - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione raccolta - quintali	superficie totale - ettari	superficie in produzione - ettari	produzione totale - quintali	produzione raccolta - quintali	
Tipo di coltivazione									
altra frutta a guscio
pistacchi	5	5	56	53	5	5	56	53	

Chart A1.13. Pistachio production in Basilicata, data source ISTAT.

ANNEX 2: Example of form administered by Google Form tool for the survey on agricultural productions and waste.

The screenshot shows a Google Form interface. At the top, there is a circular logo for the University of Basilicata (Università degli Studi della Basilicata) with the year 1982. Below the logo, the form title is 'Ecosistema NODES' with the subtitle 'Raccolta dati per la valorizzazione degli scarti produttivi'. The form is set to be shared via email at 'ecosistema_nodes@unibas.it' and is currently set to 'Non condiviso'. A red asterisk indicates that the following question is mandatory. Below this is a blue banner containing logos for the European Union, the Italian Ministry of University and Research, Italiadomani, and NODES. The form contains four text input fields, each with a red asterisk indicating it is mandatory: 'Nome Azienda, Ragione Sociale, Sede Legale', 'Tipologia di coltura' (with a subtext 'indicare anche il codice ateco'), 'Periodo di produzione' (with a subtext 'Mese del Raccolto'), and 'Area coltivata in regione' (with a subtext 'Ettari (ha)'). Each field has a placeholder text 'La tua risposta'.

Localizzazione della Coltura *

Principali Comuni di Produzione

La tua risposta

Produzione complessiva *

Quintali/ettolitri

La tua risposta

Impiego prevalente (utilizzo diretto/trasformazione) *

Destinazione d'uso della coltura, trasformazione diretta o fornitura a terzi

La tua risposta

Tipologia di scarto prevalente *

La tua risposta

Quantitativo di Scarto Prodotto *

Quintali/Ettolitri

La tua risposta

Altra tipologia di scarto (2)

La tua risposta

Quantitativo di Scarto Prodotto da Altra Tipologia (2)

Quintali/Ettolitri

La tua risposta

Altra tipologia di scarto (2)

La tua risposta

Quantitativo di Scarto Prodotto da Altra Tipologia (2)

Quintali/Ettolitri

La tua risposta

Altra tipologia di scarto (3)

La tua risposta

Quantitativo di Scarto Prodotto da Altra Tipologia (3)

La tua risposta

Attuale Metodologia di Smaltimento e/o Riutilizzo dello Scarto Prodotto *

La tua risposta

Invia

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